

**RESEARCH OF TECHNOGENIC RAW MATERIALS OF MINING
PRODUCTION****Usmonaliev Jakhongir**

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Abstract. The article discusses the results of X-ray fluorescence and atomic emission analyzes of technogenic raw materials of the mining production of JSC AGMK and JSC NMMK of the Republic of Uzbekistan, showed the content of non-ferrous metals such as copper, zinc, chromium, manganese and others. X-ray fluorescence of technogenic raw materials in the form of AGMK sludge and pulp showed the content of iron, silicon and aluminum in the composition of the pulp and sulfur, calcium and yttrium in the composition of the pulp in large quantities. Atomic emission analysis of technogenic raw materials GMZ-1 showed that the composition contains significant amounts of precious metals in the amount of 1,26 g/t of silver and 0,375 g/t of gold, copper and zinc were also found in the composition, uranium, chromium, nickel, ect.

Keywords: X-ray fluorescence analyses, atomic emission analyses, technogenic raw materials, uranium, chromium, JSC AMMC, SPA NMMK.

Introduction. The main reason for the relatively low level of use of raw material resources of deposits is that if the extracted rock contains several useful components

[1, p. 103], mining and metallurgical enterprises, for the most part, are focused on obtaining only one type of marketable product. Therefore, significant reserves of secondary mineral raw materials accumulate in dumps [2, p. 280]. According to experts, the practical implementation of already developed technical solutions for the development of technogenic deposits [3, p. 10] will reduce the volume of mineral extraction by 20-30%. During flotation enrichment of copper-molybdenum ores, the yield of waste tailings [4, p. 17], almost equal to the volume of processing of the feedstock, which is due to the low content of the main components in it. Tailings storage is associated with high material costs [5, p. 64] and causes irreparable harm to the environment [9, p. 25]. At the same time, tailings from the processing of copper ores are an additional source of copper, molybdenum, gold, silver, as well as valuable raw materials for the production of non-metallic useful components [6, p. 115] (quartz, mica, kaolin, etc.), building materials (cement, brick, ceramic tiles, etc.), chemical raw materials (pyrite) [7, p. 20] and ferrous metal concentrate – magnetite.

Goal of the work.

The purpose of this study is to analyze technogenic waste from mining production at the Kalmakir and Muruntau deposits using modern highly sensitive equipment.

Instruments and reagents.

We used in the work: High-performance energy-dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectrometer – Rigaku NEX CG EDXRF Analyzer with Polarization in set – 9022 19 000 Japan; emission spectrometer with inductively coupled plasma ICPE-9000 “Shimadzu”, Kyoto Japan; concentrated sulfuric acid H_2SO_4 (reagent grade), ordinary chemical and measuring glassware.

Objects and methods of research

The objects for analysis were technogenic waste from the copper smelter (MPS) of the Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Combine and hydrometallurgical plant No. 1 of the Navoi MMC. X-ray fluorescence and inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy methods were used for the analysis. Based on preliminary

results of analysis of sludge and pulp samples, the presence of the following components was established in them: Fe_2O_3 , SiO_2 , CaO , MgO , ZnO and CuO .

Atomic emission spectroscopy with inductively coupled plasma has established that samples of technogenic raw materials contain both base metals and precious and trace elements. The significant content of precious metals gold (Au) and silver (Ag) in the sludge of NMMC in comparison with those of a number of AGMK enterprises is explained by the fact that the initial raw material itself - the ore of the Muruntau deposit, used by Hydrometallurgical Plant 1 of NMMC, is initially rich in gold, silver and uranium, in while the ore of the Kalmakir deposit, processed at the AMMC, is polymetallic and the main macrocomponent is copper (Cu).

Results and discussion

X-ray fluorescence analysis of sludge samples showed that most of its composition contains iron - 46.5%, followed by silicon 21.4% and aluminum 4.54%. There are also many other elements that are of great importance for the national economy: magnesium (Mg), sulfur (S), calcium (Ca), potassium (K), copper (Cu), zinc (Zn) and many others. The results of X-ray fluorescence analysis are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

X-ray fluorescence analysis of CSP sludge samples

№	Sample	Content (%) element oxide	№	Sample	Content (%) element
	Tails CSP			Tails CSP	
1	MgO	0.903	1	Mg	0,690
2	Al_2O_3	6.73	2	Al	4.54
3	SiO_2	35.7	3	Si	21.4
4	SO_3	2.93	4	S	1.50
5	K_2O	1.84	5	K	1.98
6	CaO	2.00	6	Ca	1.86
7	TiO_2	0.427	7	Ti	0.330
8	Cr_2O_3	0.0594	8	Cr	0.0547
9	MnO	0,0560	9	Mn	0.0176

10	Fe ₂ O ₃	47.2	10	Fe	46.5
11	CuO	0.512	11	Cu	0.564
12	ZnO	0.813	12	Zn	0,902
13	Ga ₂ O ₃	0.27	13	Ga	0.348
14	As ₂ O ₃	0.0365	14	As	0.389
15	Rb ₂ O	0.0206	15	Rb	0.256
16	SrO	0.94	16	Sr	0.109
17	ZrO ₂	0.238	17	Y	1.8
18	MoO ₃	0.173	18	Zr	2.44
19	SnO ₂	0.51	19	Mo	1.59
20	Sb ₂ O ₃	0.78	20	Sn	5.5
21	BaO	0.679	21	Sb	8.86
22	PbO	0.194	22	Ba	8.07
23	U ₂ O ₃	0.29	23	Pb	2.45
24	Na ₂ O	0.57	24	U	3.9

A study of the composition of the slag shows a significant content of iron, silicon, aluminum, potassium, aluminum, etc. It is noteworthy that the composition of the slag sample contains 3.9% uranium, which makes the technogenic waste of the AMMC mining production radioactive.

The initial X-ray diffraction pattern of the CSP sludge is shown in Figure 1

Fig. 1 . X-ray fluorigram of CSP sludge samples

The results of fluorescent analysis of MPZ pulp samples and fluorescent radiographs are shown in Table 2 and Figure 2, respectively.

Table 2.

X-ray fluorescence analysis of CSP pulp samples

№	Sample	Content (%) element oxide	№	Sample	Content (%) element oxide
	Tails CSP			Tails CSP	
1	Cl ₂ O	0.368	1	Cl	0,336
2	Al ₂ O ₃	1.28	2	Al	0.558
3	SiO ₂	5.58	3	Si	2.27
4	SO ₃	56.1	4	P	0.742
5	K ₂ O	0.204	5	S	48.9
6	CaO	34.5	6	K	0.170
7	TiO ₂	0.418	7	Ca	24.8
8	Cr ₂ O ₃	3.78	8	Ti	0.0248
9	MnO	0.23	9	Mn	0.0081
10	Fe ₂ O ₃	0.513	10	Fe	0.161
11	CuO	0.13	11	Cu	0.47
12	ZnO	0.15	12	Zn	0.42
13	SeO ₂	0.02	13	As	3.5
14	Rb ₂ O	0.003	14	Se	0.547
15	SrO	0.0212	15	Rb	0.145
16	Y ₂ O ₃	0.019	16	Sr	0.824
17	ZrO ₂	0.445	17	Y	6.98
18	PbO	0.687	18	Zr	1.5
19	SnO ₂	0.648	19	Ag	0.0145
20	Dy ₂ O ₃	0.034	20	Sn	2.1
21	U ₃ O ₈	0.0003	21	Pb	0.21

Pic. 2 . X-ray fluorigram of CSP pulp samples

A study of the composition of the pulp shows a significant content of sulfur, calcium, arsenic, silicon, zirconium, etc. It is noteworthy that the composition of the pulp sample contains 48.9% sulfur, which makes the technogenic waste of the AMMC mining production very attractive in the production of sulfuric acid, which is widely used in almost all sectors of the national economy.

The presence of these elements in technogenic waste from mining and metallurgical production is confirmed by the results of atomic emission spectroscopy with inductively coupled plasma. The results of the analysis are presented in Table 3.

Table 3.

Results of inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-AES), g/t (GMZ-1 sludge)

№	Sample	Content (%) element oxide	№	Sample	Content (%) element oxide
	Tails GCC-1			Хвосты GCC-1	
1	Ag	1,26	26	In	0,251
2	Al	50400	27	K	20200
3	As	83,5	28	Mg	18,4
4	Au	0,375	29	Mn	399
5	Ba	565	30	Mo	3,76
6	Be	1,77	31	Na	13500
7	Bi	1,56	32	Nb	17

8	Ca	13100	33	Ni	35,4
9	Cd	0,249	34	P	606
10	Ce	42,4	35	Pb	17,6
11	Co	13,3	36	Rb	90,9
12	Cr	87,7	37	Ta	0,809
13	Er	1,34	38	Th	10,4
14	Eu	0,901	39	Ti	3340
15	Fe	39300	40	U	3,15
16	Ga	15,5	41	V	125
17	Gd	2,98	42	Zn	92,7
18	Ce	42,4	43	Pb	17,6
19	Nd	17	44	Sr	225
20	S	8740	45	W	2,12
21	Sb	0,781	46	Y	11,3
22	Sc	10,2	47	Yb	1.81
23	Se	1,04	48	Zr	69,4
24	Sm	2,99	49	Hf	1,52
25	Sn	9,12	50	Cu	50,3

A study of the composition of samples of technogenic waste from the NMMC GMZ-1 shows a significant content of precious and rare metals: gold, silver, cerium, zirconium, samarium, hafnium and others, which makes it urgent to develop innovative technologies for the extraction of these metals from sludge waste.

Conclusion

As a result of the activities of the mining industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan, large volumes of tailings dumps of technogenic waste are formed. In this regard, the problem of integrated use of mineral resources and technogenic raw materials is becoming increasingly urgent.

During the study of samples of technogenic raw materials from non-ferrous metallurgy enterprises of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a significant content of important non-ferrous metals was revealed. This allows us to predict the further use of technogenic raw materials.

X-ray fluorescence analysis of slag samples showed that the most iron in its composition is 46.5%, followed by silicon 21.4% and aluminum 4.54%. There are also

many other elements that are of great importance for various sectors of the national economy: magnesium (Mg), sulfur (S), calcium (Ca), potassium (K), copper (Cu), zinc (Zn) and others. Waste from the AGMK copper smelter can be used as the main component of building materials (cement, brick, ceramic tiles, etc.), chemical raw materials (pyrite) and ferrous metal concentrate - magnetite. And in the sludge samples of Hydrometallurgical Plant No. 1 NMMC, modern physicochemical and physical analysis methods revealed a significant content of noble metals gold (Au) and silver (Ag), as well as radioactive uranium (U), which provides prerequisites for further research on the additional extraction of these valuable components and deep processing of secondary raw materials within the framework of the Green Chemistry concept.

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